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Research Article

A Comparative Study on The Effects of Arni and Beta Blocker on Renal Function in Patients with Heart Failure

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ABSTRACT

Heart failure (HF) is a multi faceted clinical syndrome classified based on ejection fraction into heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF) and preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF). Renal dysfunction is frequently observed in HF and serves as a strong predictor of adverse outcomes. Recent advancements have highlighted the therapeutic potential of angiotensin receptor blocker-neprilysin inhibitors (ARNIs), not only in improving cardiac outcomes but also in preserving renal function. This study aims to evaluate the renal benefits of ARNI therapy in comparison to beta blockers in HF patients. A prospective observational study was conducted over a six-month period at Durgabai Deshmukh Hospital, Hyderabad, including 100 diagnosed HF patients, categorized into HFrEF and HFpEF groups. Renal parameters such as serum creatinine, glomerular filtration rate (GFR), blood urea nitrogen (BUN) and brain natriuretic peptide (BNP) levels were monitored. The outcomes of ARNI therapy were statistically compared with those of beta blockers using t-test and chi-square test. The findings revealed a significant reduction in serum creatinine levels in HFrEF patients receiving ARNI, along with a notable decrease in BNP levels across both HFrEF and HFpEF groups. While serum electrolyte levels remained stable with ARNI therapy, an improvement in GFR was predominantly observed in the HFrEF group. These results suggest that ARNI therapy offers considerable renal protection in heart failure patients, especially those with HFrEF, and may serve as a superior alternative to conventional beta blocker therapy in managing both cardiac and renal aspects of HF.

INTRODUCTION

A chronic condition known as heart failure (HF) develops when the heart is unable to pump blood efficiently enough to fulfill the body's oxygen

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uptake needs. Heart failure may develop from any condition that effects the heart's ability to beat (diastolic dysfunction) or relax (systolic dysfunction). The abbreviation HFrEF stands for heart failure associated with reduced ejection fraction, often known as diminished left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF). Maintaining left ventricular systolic function (normal LVEF) with suspecting diastolic deterioration is what called as heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF).^[1]

Table No.1- Classification Of Heart Failure

Classification	Ejection Fraction (%)
HFrEF	Less than 45%
HFpEF	Greater than 50%

Etiology

There are many causes of HF, and coronary artery disease (CAD) causing ischemic heart disease is the most common cause. Ischemic heart disease is by far the most common cause of HF worldwide. Ischemia leads to a lack of blood flow to heart muscles, reducing the EF^[2]. Valvular heart disease is another common intrinsic heart condition that can cause HF. Rheumatic heart disease is the most common cause of valvular heart disease in children and young adults worldwide. It is caused by an immune response to group A Streptococcus and primarily causes mitral and aortic stenosis^[3]. Hypertension causes HF even in the absence of CAD or ischemic heart disease. High blood pressure causes mechanical stress by increased afterload and neuro hormonal changes that increase ventricular mass. HTN is also strongly associated with other comorbidities for HF development, and aggressively treating hypertension is shown to lower the incidence of HF. Cardiomyopathy is a heterogeneous group of diseases characterized by enlarged ventricles with impaired function not related to secondary causes such as ischemic heart disease, valvular heart disease, hypertension, or congenital heart disease. The most common types of cardiomyopathies are hypertrophic, dilated, restrictive, arrhythmogenic right ventricular,

and left ventricular non compaction. In addition to HF, cardiomyopathy can present as arrhythmia or sudden cardiac death, further compelling the identification of underlying disorders^[4]. Obesity is a leading cause of HF in patients younger than 40 years, Patients with obesity are more likely to have HFpEF, possibly secondary to adipose-produced cytokines such as IL-1b, IL-8, and TNF α . Adipose tissue also degrades natriuretic peptides^[5].

Signs And Symptoms

Pulmonary symptoms: The major symptoms, which include dyspnea (especially with exercise) and fatigue, make physical activity intolerable, orthopnea, tachypnea, cough, nocturnal paroxysmal dyspnea, Peripheral edema, pulmonary embolism, fluid retention. **Nonspecific symptoms:** Fatigue, nocturia, hemoptysis, stomach discomfort, anorexia, nausea, bloating, changes in mental state, weight gain^[6].

Pathophysiological Differences Between HFpEF and HFrEF

Evidence-based treatment improves symptoms and prognosis only in HFrEF but not in HFpEF. These variations underline how important it is to comprehend how the pathophysiology of HFrEF and HFpEF differs, as this may also affect the therapy goals. The high death rate and rising incidence are shared by both. Variations in the pathological development of HFrEF and HFpEF have been documented in relation to fibrosis, changes in the giant spring titin, cardiomyocyte hypertrophy and death, inflammation, and endothelial function^[7]. Cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, intercellular fibrosis, altered cardiomyocyte relaxation, and inflammation are some of the anatomical and cellular changes that characterize HFpEF and impair the left ventricle's ability to relax. Chronic comorbid conditions such as arterial hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), obesity, renal insufficiency, lung illness, liver disease, sleep apnea, gout, and cancer are frequently linked to HFpEF. These concomitant conditions, such as diabetes, which also activate inflammation, are frequently associated with the inflammatory process in

HFpEF. About 60% of non-cardiomyocytes are endothelial cells, and HFpEF is more likely than HFrEF to have endothelial dysfunction, which is frequently observed early in cardiovascular disease. Numerous adaptive processes, such as neurohumoral activation, vasoconstriction, increased oxidative stress, nitric oxide imbalance, or energy bioavailability, might lead to endothelial dysfunction after decreased cardiac output^[7]. However, in HFpEF, endothelial dysfunction (caused by comorbidities) may also be a prelude to cardiac dysfunction. There is a wide range of variability in HFpEF. In addition to being older, patients with HFpEF are twice as likely to be female^[8]. There may be a link between a higher incidence of myocardial infarction and the prevalence of men in HFrEF. The hallmark of HFrEF is a significant loss of cardiomyocytes, either acutely or chronically, which leads to systolic dysfunction. Examples of such conditions include myocardial infarction-related myocyte loss, genetic mutations, myocarditis with cell loss, or valvular disease with overload-induced cell death (apoptosis antigen 1 activation)^[9,10], which is followed by an inability of the left ventricle to contract normally. The most common feature in HFpEF is concentric cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, which might result in eccentric remodeling with an excess of fibrotic tissue. Moreover, cardiomyocytes in HFrEF have reduced myofibrillar density, are more elongated, and are thinner^[11]. Both HFrEF and HFpEF have distinct effects on cardiac titin and calcium levels. Although HFmrEF can develop into either HFrEF or HFpEF, like HFrEF, its phenotype is primarily characterized by coronary artery disease.

Diagnosis

- Patients exhibiting HF side symptoms should be carefully considered for HF diagnosis. In addition to pertinent research center work, patients with HF should have a thorough history and physical evaluation.
- Conditions that might cause or destroy HF are typically evaluated with a full blood count, serum electrolytes (including calcium and magnesium),

urinalysis, lipid profile, thyroid capability tests, glycosylated hemoglobin (A1C), and B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) generally at 100 pg/mL.

- Although systolic or diastolic dysfunction cannot be definitively determined by calculating the left ventricular discharge fraction (LVEF), echocardiography may differentiate abnormalities of the pericardium, myocardium, and cardiovascular valves.
- The main goal of the doctor's subjective assessment based on the NYHA Functional Classification System for Patients with Symptomatic HF is this. Physical activity levels are completely up to the discretion of the patients in Functional Class (FC)-I. The limits experienced by FC-II patients are mild, those of FC-III are substantial, and those of FC-IV are severe.
- Electrocardiograms and chest x-rays may also reveal ventricular enlargement (ECG). Pulmonary edema and pleural effusions are other possible findings on a chest x-ray. In order to assess systolic and diastolic dysfunction, echocardiography may measure the left ventricular ejection fraction and rule out problems with the myocardium, pericardium, or cardiovascular valves (LVEF)^[12].
- Blood examinations: Blood tests to measure certain chemicals, like brain natriuretic peptide external link (BNP), may be prescribed by physician. When heart failure occurs, these levels rise.

Ejection Fraction Measurement

To determine ejection fraction, physician may prescribe an echocardiogram (echo) or other imaging procedures. The percentage of blood in the left ventricle, the lower left chamber of the heart, that is pumped out of the heart with each heartbeat is known as your ejection fraction. The Ejection Fraction is a measure of cardiac pumping efficiency^[13].

Treatment

Beta Blockers: Decrease in hospitalizations, mortality, and disease progression are all observed

in patients with systolic heart failure (HF) who take particular β -blockers, as supported by substantial evidence from clinical trials. In the absence of contraindications or a documented history of β -blocker intolerance, the ACC/AHA guidelines advise treating all stable individuals with HF and a decreased LVEF with β -blockers. Even if patients' symptoms are well-controlled with ACE inhibitor and diuretic medication, they should nevertheless receive a β -blocker. Optimizing ACE inhibitor dosages prior to initiating a β -blocker is not necessary, as the addition of a β -blocker is probably more advantageous than an increase in ACE inhibitor dose. For asymptomatic patients with a decreased LVEF (stage B), β -blockers are also advised in order to lower the chance of developing HF. In stable individuals with little to no indication of fluid excess, start β -blockers. Owing to their adverse inotropic effects, begin β -blockers at very low dosages and titrate up gradually to prevent symptom exacerbation or rapid decompensation. When it's feasible, titrate to target doses to maximize survival benefits. Large HF trials have demonstrated that the only β -blockers that reduce mortality are bisoprolol, carvedilol, and metoprolol succinate (CR/XL). The options are usually restricted to either carvedilol or metoprolol succinate since bisoprolol is not readily accessible in the required 1.25 mg starting dose. In placebo-controlled clinical trials, the initial and target doses are those that are linked to decreased mortality. Until the target dose or the maximally tolerated dose is attained, doses should be doubled no more frequently than every two weeks, as tolerated. Patients should be aware that reaching the target dose is crucial to maximizing benefits from dose up-titration, which is a lengthy and slow process. Additionally, there's a chance that the therapy

won't work right away and that the HF symptoms will get worse right after starting.

ARB-Nepriylsin Inhibitor (ARNI):

Angiotensin receptor/nepriylsin inhibitor valsartan/sacubitril is authorized for the treatment of HFrEF. The medication is a crystalline compound made up of both medications. Among the enzymes that degrade endogenous natriuretic peptides is nepriylsin. Because the peptides induce diuresis, natriuresis, enhanced glomerular filtration, and vasodilation, they are advantageous. Sacubitril is a prodrug that inhibits nepriylsin and promotes vasodilation through a different mechanism than ARBs. Sacubitril cleaves into its active form. Nepriylsin alone would cause increased levels of AT2, however combination with valsartan removes this effect[14],[15],[16],[17].

Aim And Objective:

Aim: Assessing the efficacy of ARNI and Beta blockers on renal function in heart failure patients is the main goal of this study.

Objectives:

- In order to learn how ARNI affects renal function in heart failure patients whose ejection fraction is low.
- Determine how ARNI affects renal function in heart failure patients whose ejection fractions are maintained.
- To compare the efficacy of ARNI with Beta blockers.
- An essential result is the evaluation of the patient's quality of life.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design: A prospective observational study was conducted over a period of six months in the Departments of Cardiology and Nephrology at Durgabai Deshmukh Hospital and Research Centre, Hyderabad.

Study Population: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with heart failure were enrolled. Patients were categorized into two groups based on ejection fraction.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age ≥ 18 years
- Diagnosed HF (HFrEF or HFpEF)
- Receiving ARNI or beta-blocker therapy

Exclusion Criteria

- Acute kidney injury or ESRD
- Dialysis or kidney transplant
- Pregnant/lactating women

Data Collection:

Patient case records and lab reports were used to collect demographic data, echocardiographic findings, renal function parameters (serum creatinine, GFR, BUN), serum electrolytes, and BNP levels.

Ethical Considerations:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using Student's t-test and Chi-square test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this study, a total of 100 case reports were reviewed and categorized into HFrEF and HFpEF groups. Parameters such as serum electrolytes, creatinine, GFR, BUN, and BNP levels were evaluated using ARNI (drug 1) and Beta blocker (drug 2) and their efficacies were compared.

Table no. 1.1 – serum electrolyte values in subjects administered with drug 1 along with mean and standard deviation.

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
Na	HFpEF	134.92	4.80	0.952
	HFrEF	134.82	6.72	
k	HFpEF	4.03	0.82	0.705
	HFrEF	3.92	0.72	
Cl	HFpEF	102.47	9.0367	0.485
	HFrEF	100.65	6.7322	
Ca	HFpEF	3.05	1.31	0.354
	HFrEF	2.60	1.20	

Table No 1.2 – Serum Electrolyte Values in Subjects Administered with Drug 2 Along with Mean and Standard Deviation.

Serum electrolytes	Diagnosis	Mean	Standard deviation	P value
Na	HFpEF	122.22	33.02	0.196
	HFrEF	137.81	4.29	
K	HFpEF	4.36	0.44	0.933
	HFrEF	4.37	0.69	
Cl	HFpEF	99.56	5.96	0.869
	HFrEF	99.87	3.64	

Figure no.1 – bar diagram representing the comparison of serum electrolytes in drug 1 and drug 2.

No significant differences were observed in serum sodium, potassium, chloride, or calcium between the two groups ($p > 0.05$).

Table no 2.1- Serum Creatinine Values in Drug 1

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
SC_D1	HFpEF	1.65	1.35	0.399
	HFrEF	1.97	1.28	
SC_D2	HFpEF	1.53	1.17	0.482
	HFrEF	1.78	1.28	
SC_D3	HFpEF	1.44	1.11	0.888
	HFrEF	1.49	1.35	

Table No 2.2 – Serum Creatinine Values in Drug 2

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
SC_D1	HFpEF	1.55	0.94	0.399
	HFrEF	1.77	1.09	
SC_D2	HFpEF	1.82	1.10	0.482
	HFrEF	1.98	1.02	

Figure No.2 - Bar Diagram Representing the Comparison of Serum Creatinine Values in Drug 1 And Drug 2

ARNI therapy significantly reduced serum creatinine levels in HFrEF patients. Beta-blockers showed minimal change.

	HFrEF	78.25	11.19	
GFR_D3	HFpEF	78.80	13.83	0.725
	HFrEF	80.08	11.61	

Table no 3.1- GFR Values When Drug 1 Was Given

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
GFR_D1	HFpEF	78.96	12.15	0.374
	HFrEF	75.80	12.66	
GFR_D2	HFpEF	79.12	11.92	0.793

Table no3.2 – GFR Values When Drug 2 Is Given

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
GFR_D1	HFpEF	74.00	13.22	0.374
	HFrEF	73.81	10.77	
GFR_D2	HFpEF	76.56	13.84	0.793
	HFrEF	77.49	10.73	

Figure no.3- bar diagram representing the comparison of GFR values in drug 1(ARNI) and drug 2(beta blocker)

Both groups showed improvements, but the ARNI group had slightly better outcomes, especially in HFrEF patients.

	Drug 2	352.60	309.48	
BNP_D2	Drug 1	440.06	326.19	0.271
	Drug 2	352.92	309.196	

Table no 4.1 – Bun values when Drug 1 is Given

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
BUN D2	Drug 1	14.58	7.52	<0.001
	Drug 2	66.40	62.96	
BNP_D1	Drug 1	453.52	334.40	0.210

Table no 4.2- BUN values when drug 2 is given

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
BUN	HFpEF	43.22	35.95	0.017
	HFrEF	79.44	71.75	

Figure No.4- Bar Diagram Representing the Comparison of BUN Values in Drug 1 And Drug 2

ARNI therapy resulted in a statistically significant decrease in BUN levels ($p < 0.001$). Beta-blocker group showed higher BUN, particularly in HFrEF.

BNP_D3	HFpEF	710.36	172.90	<0.001
	HFrEF	144.44	100.86	

Table no 5.1 – BNP Levels When Drug 1 Was Given

	Diagnosis	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
BNP_D1	HFpEF	759.60	144.40	<0.001
	HFrEF	147.44	110.80	
BNP_D2	HFpEF	734.64	158.44	<0.001
	HFrEF	145.48	105.74	

Table NO 5.2- BNP Levels When Drug 2 Was Given

	Diagnosis	Mean	Standard Deviation	P value
BNP_D1	HFpEF	752.78	76.22	<0.001
	HFrEF	127.50	4.06	
BNP_D2	HFpEF	752.78	75.66	<0.001
	HFrEF	128.00	4.11	

Figure No.5 – Bar Diagram Representing the Comparison of BNP Values in Drug 1 And Drug 2

BNP levels decreased significantly in both HF_rEF and HF_pEF patients treated with ARNI ($p < 0.001$).

Conflict Of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest regarding this investigation.

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CONCLUSION

Our study demonstrates that ARNI therapy offers significant renal benefits in heart failure patients. It effectively lowers serum creatinine in HF_rEF and reduces BNP levels in HF_pEF, showing better outcomes compared to beta blockers. These results highlight ARNI's dual advantage in improving both cardiac and renal function, supporting its role as a superior therapeutic choice in heart failure management.

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